

Generative Design of Modular/Industrial Architectural System

WILSON GIOVANNY ZARATE GRANADOS

Supervisors:

Bruno Acácio Ferreira de Figueiredo

School of Architecture, Art and Design, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Filipe Jorge da Silva Brandão

Grupo CASAIS, Braga, Portugal

Abstract

One of the recurring problems in the construction industry is its recognised lack of productivity due to different factors, among which could be highlighted the fragmentation of the information flow between the different phases of the project life cycle and the difficulty in communication between the different stakeholders. To address this, the industry has reacted through the use of prefabrication and the implementation of new technologies such as Building Information Modelling. The aim is to improve both productivity, through mass customisation, and the flow of information between phases and stakeholders in the projects, through the use of software and platforms, which also give the possibility of automation with processes such as Generative Design.

The dissertation investigates the use of these technologies in the area of prefabrication in construction, focusing on the current implementation of configurators and the associated automation that could be derived from their use for the development of projects. Taking a hybrid prefabrication system (wood and concrete) currently used by CASAIS company as a case study, the research seeks to develop a framework that exploits the modular characteristics of these systems, especially in the design phase. It is in this phase where it is possible to take

advantage of the limited number of parameters of the prefabricated elements in automating the generation of design proposals and in obtaining information related to KPIs, which would, in turn, allow a more objective feasibility analysis during this first phase of the project.

The indicated solution is, firstly, the proposal of a methodology to develop a configurator applied to the case study, which uses tools and/or platforms, that are currently present in the market related to BIM and the construction industry. Then the dissertation continues with the specific development of the section of the methodology corresponding to the generation of the computational model, and for this purpose visual programming is used, taking as initial information the relevant parameters and data to be obtained that are typical of the prefabrication system studied.

The research seeks to make a contribution to the current progress in terms of productivity and information flow that has been developed in the construction industry with the implementation of prefabrication and BIM. With the use of configurators, associated with these new technologies, an incursion into automation methods is proposed, especially in the project gestation phases through Generative Design. Thus, by making use of the mass customisation possibilities offered by prefabrication systems and the integration of non-professional agents, (taking advantage of the ease of use of the configurators), a more integrated design process and a more objective decision-making process can be achieved, since it is based on more accurate data related to the feasibility of the projects.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/pUY-TIcrgDg>

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10034177